

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical foundations of the development of the professional-creative competence of future teachers, in particular, the current issues, are studied. Also, theoretical-methodological aspects and tasks of increasing students' creativity and creativity were analyzed.

Key words: professional activity, training, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology, competence, creative, professional.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the knowledge, skills, and qualifications of students of higher education institutions worldwide, developing their intellectual maturity, increasing the quality of education, humanizing it, introducing healthy technologies into the educational system, coherence and continuity, development and socialization tasks are being set to ensure the goals, to increase the creativity of specialists, including training.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Issues of formation and development of teacher's professional-creative competence V.A. Adolf, T.G. Braje, E.F. Zeera, I.A. Zimnyaya, N.V. Kuzmina, M.I. Lukyanova, A.K. Markova, A.M. Novikova, G.S. Trofimova, G. Bernhard, V. Bloom, H. Markus, It has been studied by many philosophers, pedagogues and psychologists such as R.Sterner.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Currently, the education system is characterized by significant changes, as a result of which, first of all, innovation processes are activated.

Today, the education system is significantly influenced by external factors. Radically new requirements are placed on it, their constant growth is caused by a number of global development trends:

- accelerating the pace of society's development requires preparing students for life in rapidly changing conditions;
- with a significant expansion of the scope of intercultural interaction, communication skills and tolerance of school graduates are of particular importance;

- the emergence and intensification of global problems require young people to have a modern way of thinking in order to solve them;
- democratization of the society, expansion of political and social choice opportunities collides with the need to form the readiness of the citizens for such a choice in the school;
- the rapid development of the economy and deep structural changes in the field of employment, which determines the constant need for professional development and retraining of employees, requires the formation of the desire and ability of school graduates to learn throughout their lives.

School change to meet these demands, this process must be continuous. All this can be done by an independent, active teacher who is flexible to the changes that are taking place, who takes responsibility, who values his own development, who is able and ready to learn continuously. Thus, first of all, there are special requirements for the development of the teacher's professional qualifications.

Competence as a scientific problem does not yet have a clear and precise definition, and despite the fact that interest in it has a significant history of development, it has not been fully analyzed.

Any group, team or person in the society, having high qualifications and knowledge in a certain field, becomes the owner of competence in his field and regularly improves this authority. This issue is approached in the interests of society. By improving his competence, the person, first of all, realizes his vital interests, and at the same time, he reaches the level of the society's demands on the person.

We made a proposal above to combine the concepts of "competence" and "competence" recommended by world scientists. Analyzing scientific works on the approach from the point of view of competence, we clearly notice that there are different opinions about these two concepts. According to A.G. Bermus, "Competence unites all the feelings, knowledge, experience, in general, the whole being of the improving person into a single system." "Competence is not only that a person is knowledgeable, but also that he continuously updates his knowledge," says M.A. Choshanov. According to M. Aronov, competence means that the specialist is ready for a certain activity. The ability to act in uncertain situations is competence.

Recognition of competence as a basic concept in global educational practice is characterized by its following features:

- combines the intellectual and skills of the educational structure;

- includes the interpretation of educational content formed on the basis of the "exit standard";

- has an integral nature (covers a number of the same or similar knowledge and skills related to wide areas of culture and activity: information, legal, etc.).

Based on experience and observations, competence can be considered a category consisting of five main components:

- deep understanding of the nature of the tasks being performed and the problems being solved;

- good knowledge of the existing experience in this field, active assimilation of its achievements;

- the ability to choose means and methods of action suitable for specific conditions of place and time;

- a sense of responsibility for the achieved results;

- the ability to learn from mistakes and make corrections in the process of achieving goals.

In fact, the concept of competence entered the field of education as a result of the scientific research of psychologists. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, in unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, and develops consistently. and possessing a plan of action in complex processes.

A.V. Khutorsky believes that the concepts of "competence" and "competence" can be distinguished as follows. Competence is a combination of personal qualities of a person (knowledge, skills, experience, methods of activity) and is a qualitative and effective activity of a person in relation to things and processes in a certain area. Competence means that a person has a set of competencies that express his personal attitude to the types of activities and meet the requirements.

Also, competences require constantly enriching knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work. It is considered a real, formed personal quality based on knowledge, and it is an intellectual and personally defined social and professional formation of a person. It also includes a set of interrelated characteristics (knowledge, skills, methods of operation) that are determined in relation to certain objects and processes and are necessary for high-quality production activities in relation to them. takes

Therefore, a certain isolated, special requirement for students' preparation in the educational process is considered.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the modern approach to the quality of education shows that in general education schools students should study and learn throughout their lives, regularly increase their knowledge and experience independently, and be able to solve problems in everyday life using life experience. being able to create a database, to be able to choose the main ones and to be able to analyze them are effective factors.

As can be seen from the above, there are many debates about competence and its place in society. Understanding the basic elements of universal competence in the field of education is one of the main problems of modern pedagogy. Regarding the issue of basic competence, there are many opinions on the application of the experience of world pedagogues or the determination of competence criteria based on the norms of traditional Uzbek pedagogy, and there are still many unresolved issues. If we look at the scientific research conducted in this regard, we notice that a lot of attention is paid to various fields and specialties, the development of science, teaching methods, and technologies. But it can be noted that the issue of understanding these pedagogical methods and applying them in practical activities has become one of the most urgent problems.

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